

Grammar-Based Action Selection Rules for Scriptless Testing

Parabank Experiment

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Parabank SUT Results

1. Open Account Form

Open New Account

What type of Account would you like to open?

CHECKING

A minimum of 100,00 \$ must be deposited into this account at time of opening.
Please choose an existing account to transfer funds into the new account.

12345

OPEN NEW ACCOUNT

Open Account Parabank Form

Open Account Form - Random mechanism Deviation

Open Account Form- Human mechanism Deviation

2. Update Profile Form

Update Profile

First Name:

Last Name:

Address:

City:

State:

Zip Code:

Phone #:

Parabank Update Profile Form

Update Profile Form - Random mechanism Deviation

Update Profile Form - Human mechanism Deviation

3. Transfer Funds Form

Transfer Funds

Amount: \$

From account # to account #

TRANSFER

Parabank Transfer Form

Success Submits

Unsuccess Submits

Transfer Funds Form - Random mechanism Deviation

Transfer Funds Form - Human mechanism Deviation

4. Customer Care Form

Customer Care

Email support is available by filling out the following form.

A customer care form with a light blue background. It contains four input fields: 'Name:', 'Email:', 'Phone:', and 'Message:'. The 'Message:' field is a larger text area. Below the fields is an orange button labeled 'SEND TO CUSTOMER CARE'.

Parabank Customer Care Form

Customer Care Form - Random mechanism Deviation

Customer Care Form - Human mechanism Deviation

5. Bill Payment Form

Bill Payment Service

Enter payee information

Payee Name:

Address:

City:

State:

Zip Code:

Phone #:

Account #:

Verify Account #:

Amount: \$

From account #: ▼

Parabank Bill Payment Form

6. Find Transactions Form

Find Transactions

Select an account: ▼

Find by Transaction ID:

FIND TRANSACTIONS

Find by Date: (MM-DD-YYYY)

FIND TRANSACTIONS

Find by Date Range

Between and (MM-DD-YYYY)

FIND TRANSACTIONS

Find by Amount:

FIND TRANSACTIONS

Parabank Find Transaction Form

Success Submits

Unsuccess Submits

Find Transaction Form - Random mechanism Deviation

Find Transaction Form - Human mechanism Deviation

7. Apply for Loan Form

Apply for a Loan

Loan Amount: \$

Down Payment: \$

From account #:

APPLY NOW

Parabank Request Loan Form

Request Loan Form - Random mechanism Deviation

Request Loan Form - Human mechanism Deviation

